

Reaction of rices to bacterial blight (BE) at different growth stages

S. N. Shukla, Plant Pathology Division, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

We evaluated 37 rice varieties at maximum tillering and flowering for reaction to a local isolate of BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Reaction patterns differed (see table). Kogyoku, Chugoku 45, and DV85 were resistant (score 1 to 3) at both growth stages. Te-tep, IR1545-339, Sateng, IR8, IR22, IR24, IR26, IR34, IR42, IR52, Zenith, Cempo Selak, and Java 14 were susceptible (score 6 and above) at both stages. IR20, IR28, IR36, IR44, IR46, IR54, IR56, and IR58 developed

BB reaction of rice varieties at maximum tillering and flowering, Cuttack, India.

Variety	BB reaction ^a	
	Maximum tillering	Flowering
Kogyoku	2	1
Te-tep	7	6
Chugoku 45	3	3
IR1545-339	7	7
Zenith	7	7
DV85	1	1
Sateng	6	7
PI 231129 ^b	1	—
CAS209 ^b	4	—
Cempo selak	7	7
Java 14	7	7
IR5 ^b	3	—
IR8	8	9
IR20	4	3
IR22	8	6
IR24	7	7
IR26	6	6
IR28	5	3
IR29	4	4
IR30	6	5
IR32	3	5
IR34	6	6
IR36	6	3
IR38	7	3
IR40	3	5
IR42	7	7
IR43	7	3
IR44	6	3
IR45	7	3
IR46	7	4
IR48	7	3
IR50	7	3
IR52	7	7
IR54	5	3
IR56	5	3
IR58	5	3
IR60	3	4

^a Standard evaluation system for rice. 1980.

^b Reaction at flowering not known.

resistance with age, but IR32, IR40, and IR60 became susceptible with age. IR38, IR43, IR48, and IR50 were susceptible at maximum tillering and resistant at flowering. IR29 scored moderate (4) at

both stages. PI 231129 and IR5 were resistant at maximum tillering and CAS209 scored 4. The three did not flower; hence, their reaction at flowering was not recorded. *J*

Field evaluation of rices for tungro virus (RTV) resistance

M. Suriachandraseelan, R. Saroja, F. Vivekanandan, J. Venkatakrishnan, and K. Nilakantapillai, Paddy Experiment Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

In 1984-85 kharif, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, had a RTV outbreak that destroyed large areas of Vaigai, IET1444, Kanchi, ADT36, and TKM9. During the outbreak we evaluated 37 rices for RTV resistance. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Twenty-

five-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 28 May in 3.1- × 2.2-m plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. P and K were applied basally at 22 and 41.5 kg/ha and 100 kg N/ha was topdressed in 4 equal splits 10, 17, 24, and 31 d after transplanting (DT).

Green leafhopper (GLH) population was recorded 30 DT and RTV incidence 45 DT (see table). Nine entries showed RTV resistance (1-30% infection). IR56 and BG367-3 had less than 10% infection, and TM4966 13.1%. There seemed to be no correlation between GLH infestation and RTV incidence. *J*

Reaction of 37 rices to RTV infection, ^a Tirur, India.

Variety	Parentage	GLH (no./hill)	RTV (%)
IR56	IR4432-53-3-3/PTB 3//IR36	5	6
BG367-3	BG280-1-2/PTB33	3	9
TM4966	TKM8/ADT9//CR141-192/IR26	15	13
PY3	IR3403-267/PTB33//IR26	4	17
TKM7	Pureline selection	8	18
TKM5	Pureline selection	8	20
IR36	IR1561-228-1-2//IR24-4/ <i>O. nivara</i> ///CR94-13	7	23
TM9400	IR8/Kalinga I//IR34/CH1039	13	25
TM1324	TKM9 mutant 20 Kr	15	27
TM10265	ADT31/IR8	11	37
IR58	IR28/Kwang chang Ai//IR36	6	39
IR60	IR4432-53-33/PTB33//IR36	9	44
Kannagi	IR8/TKM6	27	46
TKM6	GEB24/Co 18	8	49
IR50	IR2153-14/IR28//IR36	10	51
TM4660	ADT31/CH46	25	53
TM10253	ASDI/AS3704	10	55
TM1323	TKM9 mutant 20 Kr	20	58
TM10173	IET4786/IR36	19	59
ADT36	Tiruveni/IR20	17	62
TM10142	Pusa 33/ADT9	10	63
TM4345	Pelita I/IR8	18	65
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	18	65
IR52	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88//IR2061-214	6	65
TM4116	IR262/CH1039/Pusa 33/1ET2222	21	69
TKM3	Pureline selection	8	71
IET1444 (Rasi)	TN1/Co 29	25	71
TM9395	IR8/GEB24//CH1039/TKM9	16	78
TM10570	TKM9 white rice mutant (natural)	12	78
Co 33 (Karuna)	IR8/ADT27	20	83
Co 37 (Vaipi)	TN1/Co 29	31	84
TM10182	BC11-6-3/ADT16	16	90
TKM8	TKM6/TN1	14	93
TM8089	Selection from TKM9	17	94
Co 34 (Kanchi)	TN1/Co 29	26	94
TKM4	Pureline selection	8	96
TM7878	HZ31.2/CR126-42-1//JSS2-102/Kalinga I	14	97

^a CLH population was recorded at 30 DT and RTV infection at 45 DT.